

Director's Program in Improving Services for Education and Training Participants

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Abstract:- Purpose of this study was to determine: program formulation, implementation management, and obstacles faced by the head of the center in carrying out management and improving the instructor's professionalism. This study uses a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. Data collection techniques: Observation, Interview and Documentation Study Study. The subjects of this study were the head of the hall, the head of the sub-section, instructors, and trainees. The results of the study indicate that: (1) the head of the center in improving services to training participants, the formulation mechanism begins with knowing the cultural and social background, and consultation between stakeholders, instructors. Programs are prepared, long-term programs, medium-term programs and short-term programs, and all of these programs focus on the regulations of the Ministry of Transportation and instructions from the IMO (International Maritime Organization). All of this is already in the management leadership hall in the program hall to improve services. (2) The head of the hall implements the management of the hall to improve service by means of the head of the hall applying it to himself as an example for his subordinates and the head of the hall taking an approach to improve professional instructors.

Keywords:- Management, Leader Ship, and Professional Lecturer.

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of a service in achieving its goals is very dependent on its consumers, in the sense that the company provides quality services shown to its customers that they will be successful in achieving their goals. Now the quality of service has become a major concern in the competition. Service quality can be used as one of the agency's strategies to create customer satisfaction (deviana, et al, 2021). A quality education depends on the goals and what will be done in education. The existence of competition between universities demands that education always strives to improve quality, so that it excels in the competition. (Sulastri, 2017)

The definition of quality education must recognize that any education belongs to a system The availability of higher education institutions that can produce quality and highly competitive human resources , so that as a higher education strategic sector it producesresources quality and highly competitive human (Rinaldi, 2019; Udjang & Subarjo, 2019). The quality in some of the systems may be good, leading to a

reduction in the overall quality of education. Service quality is known by comparing customer expectations/interests for the ideal service with the service they actually receive. (Didham and Ofei-Manu, 2020)

If the service received or perceived is in accordance with what is expected, the perceived quality of service is good and satisfactory. If the service received exceeds customer expectations, the service quality is perceived as the ideal quality. Conversely, if the service received is lower than expected, then the service quality is perceived as bad. Thus the quality of service depends on the ability of the service provider to consistently meet the expectations/interests of its customers.(Borishade et al., 2021)

Leadership in institutions is very important to achieve institutional goals. One's leadership in school is one of the factors that determine the steps of a school. Leadership is an activity to influence people to want to work together to achieve the desired. The ways and patterns of behavior of leaders are determined by subordinates as a leadership style. Leadership as an activity to influence people to achieve institutional goals(Miftah Toha, 2012) .

Characteristics of leadership are having high work morale and vision which is characterized by (1) understanding correctly various school activities by using cognitive power and reasoning power regularly and intensively ; (2) responsive to various changes in science and technology; (3) effective communication skills; (4) look at the interests of the school as a whole; (5) think and act rationally and objectively; and (6) able to set priorities sharply". With the leadership management of the principal, it will be able to improve professional teachers(Sagala, 2014) .The success factor is seen from the way a leader can create a situation so that his subordinates appear aware to do what they want .Transformational leadership refers to leaders who succeed in moving teachers beyond personal interests directly through idealized influence (charisma), inspiration, intellectual stimulation, or individual consideration .

One of the efforts used to realize a complete human being is education, of course with an education system that can improve the quality of these human sources to become superior human beings, therefore, National Education based on Pancasila aims to increase piety to God Almighty, intelligence, skills , enhance character, strengthen personality, strengthen the spirit of nationalism, and love for the homeland, in order to grow people of development who can build

themselves and are jointly responsible for the development of the nation. (Rokhman et al., 2014)

Seafaring is a job that requires special skills and expertise to be able to work on ships, so there needs to be special training specifically for each type of work on board. The weakness of each training institution currently maximal is the lack of innovation and acceleration in providing services to seafarers training participants so that seafarers often get services that are less than the education and training institutions.

So to support the needs of seafarers in training and certification, the services to students in educational and training institutions must always be improved because they must always follow developments that refer to the International Maritime Organization. Many efforts have been made by the Ministry of Transportation to improve services in the field of education and training, especially in the marine sector. The Transportation Human Resources Development Agency, which is an Echelon 1 Institution under the Ministry of Transportation, has issued many changes to regulations in the field of marine education and training aimed at improving services to people who want to carry out education and training in marine education and training institutions (Ungureanu, 2014) .

Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic is a training institution under the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency which is engaged in marine education and training, at this institution the public can obtain 2 different types of certificates, namely Certificate of Competence (COC) and Certificate OF Proficiency (COP).(Basak, 2017)

Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic in the implementation of its training refers to the curriculum issued by the head of the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency which is contained in the head regulation NUMBER: PK.09/BPSDMP-2017 concerning the Curriculum of the Education and Training of Seafarers Skills Program which refers to the regulations of Standard Training, Certification and Watchkeeping (STCW) The 2010 Manila amendment issued by the International Maritime Organization. (Transportation, 2017)(Relations, 2017)

In serving the community, the Ministry of Transportation has issued several issues related to service standards for the community, including the issuance of Ministerial Regulation Number 19 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Service Standards in the Ministry of Transportation. Therefore, the researcher sees the need for a strategy or good management in improving public services in the field of education and skills at the Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic (Ernstsen and Nazir, 2020).

From the description above, the writer wants to do a research with the title "Director's Strategy in Improving Services for Participants in Seafaring Skills Training at the Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic". The purpose of this study is to determine: program implementation, management implementation, and the obstacles faced by the Director in carrying out management and improving the professionalism of Lecturers.

II. METHODS

This study uses a descriptive method using a descriptive approach, namely (Sugiyono, 2014)"Qualitative research is a process of exploring and understanding the meaning of individual and group behavior, describing social problems or humanitarian problems". The research site is at Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic. The data collection technique contains a sequence of procedures for using research tools. The course of the research contains the steps carried out in outline from obtaining a research permit to preparing a research report. The data and information that have been obtained are then analyzed and interpreted from the beginning of the study to the end of the study by referring to the theoretical basis related to the problem under study. Data analysis in this qualitative research is carried out by classifying, directing, removing unnecessary, and organizing data (reducing data), summarizing the main points (data display) and drawing conclusions (data verification)(Gegenfurtner, 2019). In this study, the research was conducted at the Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic, and the time of the research was carried out from May 2021 to July 2021. The research subjects in this study were a source of data to obtain information related to the director and capacity building through training. The subjects or respondents of this research were the directors or sub-sections, instructors, and participants who attended training at the Malahayati Aceh Shipping Polytechnic. The process of analyzing qualitative data is carried out before entering the field, safe in the field, and after finishing in the field.(Djam'an and A'an, 2014)

Reducing data includes summarizing, selecting the main things, focusing on the important things, looking for themes and patterns. Thus the reduced data will provide a clearer picture. Presentation of data serves to facilitate and understand what happened, as well as to plan further work based on what has been achieved so that researchers can find patterns from the data during the study, the pattern is then presented in the final report of the study. Conclusions in qualitative research are new findings that have never existed before. Findings can be in the form of descriptions or pictures of an object that was previously dim or dark so that after research it becomes clear, it can be in the form of causal or interactive relationships, hypotheses or theories.

In qualitative data analysis, we build words from the results of interviews or observations of the data needed to be described and summarized". That is, questions can be made by researchers to see the relationship between various identified themes, behavior or individual characteristics such as age and gender and so on that support this.(H, 2013).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of research on the Director's strategy in improving the services of training participants in improving skills at the Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic Aceh. Conclusions, and suggestions are described in detail as follows. The Director's Program in Improving Services for Training Participants at the Malahayati Shipping Polytechnic Aceh. The results show that the Director's program to improve professional competence in the structure is prepared at the beginning of each school year by the school development team which includes annual programs and semester programs and has not been well and neatly documented. The planned program is to provide guidance to instructors on a regular basis.

The success of a school is largely determined by the success of its leadership in managing educators and education personnel in schools. The management and management of education personnel aims to empower educational personnel effectively and efficiently to achieve optimal results, but still in comfortable and pleasant conditions. The role of the director / principal and improving the quality of human resources is very important, the principal is a very important component in improving the quality of education.

Planning is a preparation that is prepared by using the ability of reasoning for an action to be taken to achieve a goal. Planning is an essential process in the management of educational institutions. Planning is a number of pre-determined activities to be carried out at a certain period in order to achieve the stated goals". Planning is broad, complex, and takes a lot of time. The essence of planning is in the form of formulating goals and coordinating ways to achieve these goals. Planning has two very important meanings. The first is the beginning of the entire management process. Second, it aims to direct activities within the organization. (Usman and Husaini, 2014)

The results of this study are like which discusses how principals should apply leadership styles in schools. Some of the leadership styles applied by school principals consist of managerial leadership, transformational leadership, transactional leadership, instructional leadership and positive leadership. Therefore, principals do not apply leadership styles in managing schools but must be able to integrate and contextualize leadership styles based on the need to achieve school goals. (Lumban Prision, 2017). The main role of school principals in developing the quality of educators and education personnel in schools is as educators, motivators, managers, administrators, supervisors, and leaders. (Yenni, Lian and Sari, 2020)

IV. CONCLUSION

The Director's program to improve the ability of students has been well structured and effective for students, educators, and employees within the Malahayati Aceh Shipping Polytechnic. Programs that aim to approach all training parties to students, because they are customers, programs to increase the ability of educators and students

through special training, stimulation and so on, programs to provide facilities, and form new programs, namely improving English language skills. to students.

Planning activities are one way that makes activities run well, accompanied by various anticipatory steps to minimize things that happen so that these activities achieve the goals that have been set. This is needed to make it easier for schools to explain and get support from the government, from parents, both thought, moral, material and financial support to implement the plan to improve the quality of education. With the planning in the form of programs or strategies made by the principal, the results of this study greatly help the principal in carrying out the event as Director.

The director at the time of implementing but preparing the plan was very good, there are few suggestions that researchers can convey as suggestions or positive input. At the time of planning the program to be implemented, it is advisable to include all interested parties in making the program. Planning every year must be added because of the urgency of developments in the world of education today.

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